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“THE LOVE STORY OF TINKER AND JOHN”

Narrator:

***** INSTRUMENTAL *****

In life, we could never have everything. Some are lucky in their career, and some are lucky in their love life. Not all people are blessed in love; some stumble once or even many times in finding the right one. But trust God’s process—He will give you the right person at the right time. Just be patient. As they say, what is meant to be, is meant to be. This is what we call *DESTINY*. Let us be inspired by how the love story of Tinker and John began despite all the challenges thrown at them. Indeed, **LOVE WINS**.

Setting:

The story takes place at a maritime school in Cebu City.

Characters:

- **Tinker** – John’s wife, strong-willed, protagonist.
- **John** – Tinker’s persistent and loving husband, protagonist.
- **Engr. Alby** – School’s Guidance Counselor, antagonist.
- **Carlo** – John’s close friend, supportive buddy.
- **Ms. M** – Tinker’s co-teacher, antagonist.
- **Arnel & Jhuniel** – John’s school friends and buddies.

Scene 1: The First Day of School

(The classroom is noisy. As Tinker steps in, everyone stops talking.)
Music Playing... “We’re All in This Together” – High School Musical

Director: ACTION! *(Music off)*

Tinker: Good morning. I am Tinker, your English Grammar Instructor. I’m happy to see new faces this semester. Welcome to this maritime school!

Today, you will introduce yourselves one by one for two minutes. After that, I will give an overview of the subject and discuss our house rules.

Who would like to volunteer? No one? Okay... I'll call names alphabetically.
(*John stands up...*)

Tinker: John? What are you wearing? What's your name? Do you think that's appropriate for school? I'd appreciate it if you wore something more appropriate next time.

(*John nods, clearly shocked. The students react with murmuring.*)

Scene 2: The Next Meeting

Music Playing... "Congratulations" – Atkinson Girls

Tinker: Good morning! Wow! Most of you are wearing your Type A uniforms. Congratulations!
(*Students nod and thank her. Music off.*)

Tinker: Alright, class—

Carlo (interrupting): Excuse me, Ma'am. Are you single?

Tinker: That's a common question from new students. My answer is yes, but I'm not looking for anyone, okay? Did I answer your question, Carlo?

Carlo: Yes, Ma'am.

Tinker: Great. Now, let's focus on class. Please ask relevant questions next time.
(*Some students murmur, others nod.*)

Scene 3: Foundation Day

Music Playing... Foundation Day song

(*Over the phone, Tinker's name is repeatedly mentioned.*)

Tinker: Excuse me! Stop announcing my name. If you mean what you say, say it to me directly. Thank you.
(*As Tinker is about to leave, John and his friends approach her.*)

John: Excuse me, Ma'am, are you going home?

(*Tinker smiles, nods, and walks away. Music off.*)

A few minutes later...

(*Phone rings.*)

Tinker: So, this is you, John?

*(On January 28, John invites Tinker to lunch, and they have a great conversation.)
Music Playing... “Stubborn Love”*

Scene 4: The Aftermath

*(Monday morning, Tinker walks to her office. Colleagues, including Ms. M, whisper about her.)
Music off*

Ms. M: Hey, Ma’am Tinker. How was the date yesterday? I saw you with a student in a restaurant. How was it?

Tinker (shocked): I believe that’s none of your business, Ms. M.
*(On her desk, a note reads: “Please come to my office for an important talk. – Engr. Alby”)
(Tinker sighs, knowing what’s coming.)*

Engr. Alby: Ms. Tinker, someone saw you with a student.

Tinker: Is it against school rules to go out with a student? I haven’t read that in the manual. I was decent, and going out with a student doesn’t make me any less so.
(As Tinker leaves the office, people stare. Ms. M smirks triumphantly.)

Tinker: *The hell I care!*
(Since then, Tinker and John become the talk of the school. John calls...)

John: Can I come to your office, Ma’am?

Tinker: Okay.
(John arrives.)

Tinker: John, I’ve had my heart broken before because of third parties. I don’t want to go through that again. My life has been a roller coaster. You’re young—you’ll meet girls your age.

John: Ma’am, I’m thankful for your past heartbreaks. Without them, we would have never met.

Scene 5: A Year and a Half Later

*(John graduates, but Tinker doesn’t attend since she resigned to teach at a university.)
Music Playing... “What a Journey It Has Been”
(On Graduation Day, music off.)*

John: See, Babe? We’re not just a moment—we’re forever.
(Tinker smiles, knowing she made the right choice.)

Final Scene

Music Playing... "Through the Years"

Narrator: John and Tinker are now married, blessed with a five-year-old daughter. Tinker is forever grateful. Though their paths were different, love led them to each other. God gave them the greatest gift—their daughter. One day, Tinker will share their love story with her most precious child.

Their love story is one of a kind. They faced judgment, endured hardships, but in the end—**LOVE WINS.**

..... THE END

